

Implementing an Online Preceptorship Training Module for CRNAs

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Background

- The Council on Accreditation (COA) states CRNAs must serve as a preceptor to provide clinical guidance to SRNAs
- Preceptors serve as a teacher, role model, and facilitator in the clinical setting (Omansky, 2010)
- Although current literature supports the use of preceptor workshops to enhance the CRNA preceptor role, there is a lack of standardization for CRNA preceptor education

Purpose

To implement an improved online CRNA preceptor education module and evaluate its effectiveness by measuring the following outcomes: satisfaction, comfort, confidence, and knowledge

Review of Literature

- Barriers to preceptor education:
 - Time, cost, lack of preceptor education, limited access, and lack of compensation
- Benefits to preceptor education:
 - Greater self-efficacy as an educator, reinforces knowledge, addresses diverse learning styles, increases role satisfaction, refines communication, and improves clinical evaluation
- No difference between online versus in-person learning

Methods

- **Design:** Quality improvement project (QI)
- **Setting:** Kaiser Permanente Panorama City Medical Center (KPPCCMC)
- **Sample:** All CRNAs practicing at KPPCCMC

Supporting Framework

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Results

Data Findings

- Of 33 invitations, 9 completed the module
- We found no significant difference between our pre and post-surveys measuring confidence, comfort, satisfaction, and knowledge
- There was no significant relationships between the survey data and the demographic data based on Spearmans Rank-Order Correlation test.
- The education module was received positively by our participants based of the open-ended questions in the post-module surveys

Related-Samples Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test Results		
Statement	Z-value	p-value
I am satisfied with my preparation regarding education of a SRNA.	-1.66	.098
I am confident with my ability to precept a SRNA.	-.45	.655
I am comfortable with actively coaching critical thinking with my SRNA.	.00	1.000
I am comfortable working with a SRNA who may have a different personality or learning style than mine.	.00	1.000
I am confident with working with a SRNA of a different ethnic background than mine.	-1.00	.317
I am confident in providing positive feedback to a SRNA.	-1.00	.317
I am confident in providing constructive feedback to a SRNA.	.00	1.000

Participant #	What recommendations do you have to improve the module
HPT 004	Employee more the Cognitive theory of multimedia learning; specifically the principle which states that people learn better when they can advance the presentation at their own pace. I feel the first drag and match definition slide was questionable.
HPT 007	In person learning I feel would help this educational piece
HPT 009	Videos were easy and fun to watch, would suggest reframing some questions: ie: I am comfortable with actively coaching critical thinking with MY SRNA...netter to state THE SRNA
HPT 013	Make it a requirement for CRNAs to take training modules in order to precept.
HPT 032	Add audio to each slide with activity

Demographic Information

- 78% Female, 22% Male, age ranged 30-63 years, 67% had 20+ years nursing experience, and 78% had 5+ CRNA experience.
- 78% never participated in CRNA preceptor course and 56% participated in a nursing preceptor course.

Discussion

- Majority of participants have not received CRNA preceptor training, representing the current gap in CRNA education
- Positive responses from participants regarding CRNA preceptor education is promising for incorporating and sustaining a standardized program
- Online education is a feasible method to deliver preceptor training due to its ease, convenience, and flexibility

Limitations

- Difficult transition from software, Articulate Rise, to Articulate Storyline
- Small sample size despite incentivization of CEUs
- Short implementation period of three weeks
- Limited generalization due to study restricted to a group of CRNAs at one facility

Recommendations

- Future studies should compare online versus in-person preceptor education modalities
 - Hybrid models should also be explored
- Ethnic and cultural education topics should have a greater emphasis
- Further modifications to the preceptor education module should be made to increase ease of use and access

Conclusion

- No significant change in confidence, comfort, satisfaction, and knowledge
- There remains a gap in CRNA preceptor education, which includes topics on ethnic and cultural diversity
- Online delivery is a viable education method

References

